

Synthesis of 3-[4''-Aryl-(2''-4'-bithiazol)-2'-yl]-2-aryl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones and their Ester Derivatives

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Thiazolidinones are reported to possess antibacterial activities^{1,2}. In continuation of our synthetic work^{3,4}, here we report the synthesis of 5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones bearing bithiazole moiety. Ester derivatives of these compounds were also synthesised.

Compounds **2** were tested for their antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. abony*, *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* using cup-plate method in acetone medium (0.5% concentration) and the activity was compared with furazolidone⁵ as standard. The compounds showed comparable activity with that of the standard against *P. aeruginosa* but were less active against other organisms.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a AEI MS 902 spectrometer and nmr spectra on a FT-NMR (80 MHz) instrument.

(2,4'-Bithiazole)-2'-arylideneamino-4-aryl (**1**) were synthesised by reported method³.

3-[4''-Aryl-(2''-4'-bithiazol)-2'-yl]-2-aryl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones (**2**): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and mercaptosuccinic acid (0.012 mol) in anhydrous benzene (50 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath using a Dean-Stark water separator for 12 h. Excess benzene was then distilled off.

The resulting solid was extracted in 10% sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid. The solid separated was washed with

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| a; X = Y = H | i; X = CH ₃ , Y = H |
| b; X = H, Y = Cl | j; X = CH ₃ , Y = Cl |
| c; X = H, Y = CH ₃ | k; X = Y = CH ₃ |
| d; X = H, Y = OCH ₃ | l; X = CH ₃ , Y = OCH ₃ |
| e; X = Cl, Y = H | m; X = OCH ₃ , Y = H |
| f; X = Y = Cl | n; X = OCH ₃ , Y = Cl |
| g; X = Cl, Y = CH ₃ | o; X = OCH ₃ , Y = CH ₃ |
| h; X = Cl, Y = OCH ₃ | p; X = Y = OCH ₃ |

water, dried and crystallised from benzene-acetone (1 : 1) : **2a**, m.p. 180°; **b**, 175°; **c**, 174°; **d**, 198°; **e**, 181°; **f**, 171°; **g**, 197°; **h**, 182°; **i**, 187°; **j**, 186°; **k**, 174°; **l**, 192°; **m**, 178°; **n**, 171°; **o**, 191°; **p**, 198°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3050–2750br (OH of COOH), 1210 (C–O of COOH=), 1700 (C=O of COOH), 1670 cm^{-1} (C=O of ketone); **2c** M^+ 493; δ (CDCl₃), 1.36 (2H, d, CHCH₂), 4.42 (1H, t, CHCH₂), 10.67 (1H, s, COOH), 2.57 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.4 (1H, s, CH), 7.21–7.86 (11H, m, Ar, thiazole).

3-[4''-Aryl-(2''-4'-bithiazol)-2'-yl]-2-aryl-5-carboethoxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone (**3**) : Dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed through a solution of **2** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) till saturation. The solution was then refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h, then poured into ice-water and the resulting

solid was dried and crystallised from benzene-acetone (1 : 1) : **3a**, m.p. 137°; **b**, 108°; **c**, 112°; **d**, 126°; **e**, 132°; **f**, 101°; **g**, 97°; **h**, 109°; **i**, 142°; **j**, 117°; **k**, 131°; **l**, 139°; **m**, 123°; **n**, 121°; **o**, 108°; **p**, 129°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1230 (C–O of COO-), 1710 (C=O of COO-), 1670 cm^{-1} (C=O of ketone).

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